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FORMULATION, OPTIMIZATION AND EVALUATION OF RASAGILINE MESYLATE *IN SITU* NASAL GEL

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study is to formulate and evaluate nasal insitu gel of Rasagiline Mesylate. Nasal gels were prepared using combination of polymers like carbopol 934, HPMC K4M and sodium alginate and evaluated in terms of clarity, viscosity, gelation, *ex vivo* drug permeation studies. *Ex vivo* drug permeation profiles showed that formulation containing sodium alginate provided a better controlled release of the drug than the other formulations. Formulation F₃ showed better drug release of about 87.62% and it exhibited better *in situ* gelling properties, p^H, clarity and viscosity. Mucoadhesive insitu nasal gel of Rasagiline mesylate delivers the drug directly to brain and provides controlled release of the drug.

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INTRODUCTION

Nasal drug delivery due to its capability of transporting a drug to central nervous system and systemic circulation. provides promising route for drug delivery . nasal mucosa provides increased bioavailability and quick onset of action , disadvantage with nasal route is mucociliary clearance due to which drug particles get cleared from the nose before complete absorption through nasal mucosa.

In situ gelation is a process of gel formation at the site of action after the formulation has been applied at the site.

Advantages Of *In Situ* Drug Delivery:

- Increased residence time of drug in nasal cavity.
- Decreased frequency of drug administration.
- Results in rapid absorption and onset of effect.
- Avoids degradation of drug in gastrointestinal tract resulting from acidic or enzymatic degradation.
- Low dose required.
- Minimized local and systemic side effects.
- Improved bioavailability of drug.
- Direct transport into systemic circulation and CNS, is possible.
- Offers lower risk of overdose of CNS acting drug.
- Improved patient compliance.

Properties Of *In Situ* Gels:

- It should be low viscous.
- It should be free flowing to allow for reproducible administration to the nasal cavity, as droplet mist or as a spray.
- Nasal in-situ gel should have long residence time.
- The nasal in-situ gel follows phase transition mechanism and stands with the shear forces in the nasal cavity wall.

Approaches For *in Situ* Gelation:

Stimuli Responsive *in situ* Gelling Systems

1. Temperature induced Gel systems
2. p^H induced gel systems

Osmotically Induced Gelling Systems

Chemically Induced *in situ* Gelling Systems

1. Ion cross linking
2. Enzymatic cross linking
3. Photo-polymerization

Stimuli Responsive *in situ* Gelling Systems:

Physical or chemical changes in responses to small external changes in the environmental conditions.

Temperature induced *in situ* gel system

In this system, gelling of the solution is by temperature change, thus sustaining the release of drug. These hydro gels are liquid at room temperature (20°-25°C) and undergo gelation when in contact with body fluids (35°-37°C), due to increase in temperature. The polymers which show temperature induced gelation are cellulose derivatives (methyl cellulose), pluronics.

p^H induced *in situ* gelling system:

Polymers containing acidic or alkaline functional groups that respond to changes in p^H are called p^H sensitive polymers. Gelling of the solution is by p^H change.

At p^H 4.4 the formulation is free from is a free running solution which undergoes coagulation when the p^H is raised by the body fluid to p^H 7.4. The polymers which shows p^H induced gelation are cellulose and its derivatives polyvinyl acetate, polyethylene glycol.

Osmotically Induced *in situ* Gelling System:

In this method, gelling of the solution instilled is by changes in the ionic strength. It is assumed that the rate of gelation depend on the osmotic gradient across the surface of the gel. The aqueous polymer solution forms a clear solution forms a clear gel in the presence of the mono or divalent cations. The polymers which show osmotically induced gelation are gellan gum, alginates.

Chemically Induced *in situ* Gelling System:

The chemical reactions which form *in situ* gel systems are ionic crosslinking, enzymatic cross linking and photo-polymerization.

Ionic cross linking:

Certain ion sensitive polysaccharides such as carragenan, gellan gum, pectin, sodium alginate undergo phase transition in presence of various ions such as K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Na^+ .

Enzymatic cross linking:

In situ formation has not been investigated widely, it has some advantages over chemical and physicochemical approaches. For example an enzymatic process operates efficiently under physiologic conditions without need for potentially harmful chemicals such as monomers and initiators.

Photo polymerization:

A solution of monomers can be injected into a tissues site and the application of electromagnetic radiation used to form gel. Acrylate or similar polymerizable functional groups are typically used as the polymerizable groups on the individual monomers and macromere because they rapidly undergo photo-polymerization in the presence of suitable photo initiator. Photo polymerizable systems when introduced to the desired site via injection get photo cured in-situ with the help of fiber optic cables and then release the drug for prolonged period of time. A photo polymerization, biodegradable hydro gels as a tissue contacting material and controlled release carrier.

Recent advances in polymers:**Thiomers:**

Thiolated polymers or thiomers are mucoadhesive polymers which contain thiol group bearing side chains. It contains low molecular mass thiol group bearing compounds are covalently bound to a polymeric backbone. This backbone consists of well-established and safe polymers such as chitosan or poly acrylic acid.

- Thiomers exhibit mucoadhesive, permeation enhancing, controlled release as well as enzyme inhibition properties.
- These features make the thiomers technology highly interesting for non-invasive delivery routes, including in first instance the oral but also the nasal, buccal and vaginal route.

Mucoadhesion:

Thiomers are capable of forming disulfide bonds with cysteine substructures of the mucus gel layer covering mucosal membranes.

Because of this property they exhibit up to 100-fold higher mucoadhesive properties in comparison to the corresponding unthiolated polymers.

Permeation enhancement:

Thiomers are able to reversibly open tight junctions. Due to thiolation the permeation enhancing effect of polymers such as polyacrylic acid or chitosan can be up to 10-fold improved.

Enzyme inhibition:

Due to the binding of metal ions, which are needed by various enzymes to maintain their enzymatic activity, thiomers are potent reversible inhibitors of various enzymes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The drug selected for the preparation of *in situ* gel was Rasagiline mesylate which is an anti-depressant drug. Rasagiline mesylate was gifted from Hi Q Pharma Hyd. The polymers used for the formulation were HPMC, Carbopol 934 and sodium alginate. The excipients used for the formulation were sodium metabisulphite, benzalkonium chloride.

Preparation Of Nasal *In situ* Gel Bases:

Weighed quantities of benzalkonium chloride and sodium metabisulphite were dissolved in distilled water. To this, required quantity of sodium alginate as specified in the table was added and stirred for 30mins until completely dispersed. To the above dispersion, HPMC and carbopol 934P were added and allowed to hydrate overnight with gentle agitation using magnetic bead. Dispersion obtained above was stirred at 1000rpm for 10 mins. Now, to get the polymer dispersion enough water was incorporated to make up to 100mL. All the formulations were adjusted to p^H 4.5 by using 0.5 M sodium hydroxide solution.

Preparation of Gel Base:

Table 1: Preparation of Gel bases.

GEL BASE CODES	AMOUNT OF CARBOPOL 934P	AMOUNT OF HPMC K4M	AMOUNT OF SODIUM ALGINATE
G1	0.3g	0.5g	-
G2	0.3g	1.0g	-
G3	0.3g	1.5g	-
G4	0.4g	0.5g	-
G5	0.4g	1.0g	-
G6	0.4g	1.5g	-
G7	0.5g	0.5g	-
G8	0.5g	1.0g	-
G9	0.5g	1.5g	-
G10	0.45g	1.3g	-
G11	0.45g	1.0g	-
G12	0.1g	-	0.5g
G13	0.3g	-	1.0g
G14	0.5g	-	1.5g
G15	0.45g	1.0g	0.5g
G16	0.45g	1.3g	0.75g
G17	0.20g	1.3g	0.75g
G18	0.20g	1.0g	1.5g

18 gel bases were prepared using different concentrations of carbopol 934P, HPMC K4M and sodium alginate.

Preliminary Evaluation Studies Of Gel Base:

Table 2: Preliminary evaluation studies of gel base.

Gel Base Codes	Clarity	Gelation
G1	+	-
G2	+	+
G3	++	+
G4	++	-
G5	++	-
G6	+	-
G7	+	++
G8	+	++
G9	+	++
G10	+++	+++
G11	+++	+++
G12	+	+
G13	+	++
G14	+	++
G15	+	++
G16	+++	+++
G17	+	+
G18	++	+

Clarity:

+++ : Very Clear

++ : Clear

+ : Turbid

Gelation:

- : No Gelation

+ : Gelation Occurred In Few Mins And Remained For Hours

++ : Gelation Immediately Occurred And Remained For Hours

+++ : Gelation Occurs Immediately And For Prolonged Periods

++++ : Stiff Gel Formation

Optimization:

From the above table showing gelation and clarity of the gel bases G₁₀, G₁₁ and G₁₆ gel bases were selected for formulating as they showed better gelation and clarity. Formulations were prepared by adding 50mg of drug to the gel bases. These formulations were further studied for evaluation test like viscosity determination, p^H determination, *EX-vivo* permeation studies, *In vivo* drug absorption, etc.

Table 3: Formulation of Rasagiline mesylate *in situ* nasal gel.

Formulations	F1	F2	F3
Carbopol 934p	0.045g	0.045g	0.045g
Hpmc	0.13g	0.1g	0.13g
Sodium Alginate	-	-	0.075g
Drug	50mg	50mg	50mg

Evaluation Tests

Gelation:

The gelling ability was assessed by placing a drop of dispersion in a vial containing 2ml of simulated nasal electrolyte solution (SNES), freshly prepared and maintained at 37°C using a water bath the gelling ability was in terms of consistency, ability to flow freely and ability to retain gel intactness.

Viscosity

Viscosity of the *in situ* gel systems was determined using Brookfield viscometer DV-II+Pro coupled with S-94 spindle (Brookfield Engineering Laboratories Inc., MA, USA). The prepared gel formulations were transferred to the beaker. The spindle was lowered perpendicularly into the gel at 100 rpm and temperature was maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. The viscosity was determined during the cooling of the system. All the measurements were performed in triplicates.

Rheological Properties Of *In Situ* Gels

The rheological properties of *in situ* gel formulations were investigated using Brookfield LVDV-E Viscometer. The temperature was initially maintained above 40 °C. The rheological properties were measured by increasing the spindle rotational speed from 0.3 to 100 rpm, and the shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$), shear stress (τ), and viscosity (η) were recorded. All the measurements were performed in triplicates.

Determination Of p^H

One ml of the prepared gels was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask, and the solution was diluted with distilled water. The p^H of resulting solution was determined using a digital p^H meter.

Drug Content Assay

One ml of the prepared formulation was dispersed in 10 ml of methanol for 2–3 min with occasional shaking. The resulting solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm filter paper and was diluted with methanol. The amount of rasagiline in the formulation was determined spectrophotometrically at 271.6nm (Shimadzu 1800, Japan).

Gel Strength

Sample was placed in a 100 ml graduated cylinder. Gelation was carried out by placing the formulations in a thermostat at 37 °C. The strength of the gel was determined by measuring the time taken by a weight of 35 g to sink 5 cm in the gel.

Mucoadhesive Strength

Ex vivo mucoadhesive strength was determined using fresh sheep nasal mucosa. The mucosal membrane was separated by removing the underlying fat and loose tissues. The membrane was washed thrice with distilled water and phosphate buffer (p^H 6.4). Modified balance method was used to design the experiment.

Ex-vivo Drug Permeation Studies

Ex-vivo drug permeation of Rasagiline was determined using Franz-diffusion cell. The prepared nasal mucosa was mounted between the donor and receptor compartments. The receptor compartment was filled with phosphate buffer (p^H 6.4). The solution was stirred at 100 rpm and maintained at 37 °C. The gel (10 mg) was placed on the nasal mucosa and the compartments were clamped together. One ml of the sample was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals (0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 h) from receptor compartments and immediately replaced using phosphate buffer (p^H 6.4). After filtering through 0.45 μm filter and dilution, the samples were analyzed for drug content at 271.6nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Clarity:

Table 5: clarity of the *in situ* gel formulations.

Formulation	Clarity
F ₁	+
F ₂	++
F ₃	+++

Determination of p^H :

The p^H of the formulations were measured using a digital p^H meter and the p^H range of the formulations were in the range (5.5 to 6.5)

Table 6: p^H of the *in situ* gel formulations.

Formulation	p^H
F ₁	5.6
F ₂	5.5
F ₃	6.3

Determination of viscosity:

The viscosity of the formulations were measured using Brookfield viscometer and viscosities were found to be within the range.

Table 7: viscosity of the *in situ* gel formulations.

Formulation	VISCOSITY(cps)
F ₁	26.4
F ₂	15.3
F ₃	69.3

Gelation:

The gelation of the formulations were measured and they were as follows:

Table 8: Gelation of the *in situ* gel formulations.

Formulation	Gelation
F ₁	++
F ₂	+
F ₃	+++

Mucoadhesive strength:

Mucoadhesive strength of the gel increased with increase in polymer concentration.

In-vitro drug permeation studies**Standard Curve Of Rasagiline mesylate:****Table 9: Standard Curve Of Rasagiline mesylate.**

Concentration	Absorbance
5	0.132
10	0.139
15	0.221
20	0.231
25	0.239
30	0.335
40	0.438
50	0.537
60	0.636

Fig. 1Standard Curve Of Rasagiline mesylate.

In- Vitro Drug Permeation Studies:**Table 10: % Drug release of Resagiline Mesylate.**

Time (Mins)	% Drug Release		
	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
30	2.07	3.19	4.92
60	6.2	7.91	9.32
90	13.66	15.44	18.72
120	16.32	19.56	22.52
150	21.12	25.03	29.12
180	25.04	27.19	32.4
210	29.16	32.51	36.61
270	43.57	45.07	49.32
300	52.62	58.23	60.2
330	63.82	68.18	73.56
360	69.89	73.26	87.62

Fig 2: In vitro drug permeation profile of Rasagiline mesylate.

CONCLUSION

Gel bases were prepared using combinations of polymers. Depending on the clarity and gelation of gel bases G₁₀, G₁₁ and G₁₆ gel bases were selected. To these gel bases drug was added and F₁, F₂, F₃ formulations were prepared.

Prepared formulations were evaluated for clarity, pH, gelation, viscosity, mucoadhesive strength and *Ex-vivo* drug permeation. Among all formulations, F₃ formulation exhibited better *in-situ* gelling properties, mucoadhesive properties and better drug release. A lot of research has been going on in this area, hence nasal *in-situ* gels can be used for drug delivery to brain.

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